

ECOSYSTEM CHANGE ANALYSIS IN THE EUROPEAN ARCTIC PERMAFROST REGIONS (1984–2024): A MULTIDIMENSIONAL ASSESSMENT USING SATELLITE IMAGERY AND AUTOMATED TOOLS

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INTRODUCTION

- Permafrost refers to ground that remains frozen for at least two consecutive years, commonly found in Arctic and sub-Arctic regions, playing a vital role in maintaining soil stability, regulating hydrology, and supporting vegetation dynamics. Over the past five decades, permafrost has been thawing as the Arctic has warmed more than three times faster than the global average (Rantanen et al., 2022), leading to significant impacts on landscapes, ecosystems, and communities.
- As permafrost thaws, the underlying soil structure becomes unstable, leading to increased soil moisture, altered drainage patterns, and changes in nutrient availability. These environmental shifts can disrupt vegetation growth, affecting species composition, plant biomass, and overall vegetation greenness. Understanding the impact of permafrost thawing on vegetation structure is essential for assessing the broader ecological consequences in sensitive ecosystems.
- The aim of our study is to investigate ecosystem dynamics between 1984 to 2024, focusing on vegetation and water bodies using space-time data cubes of spectral indices derived from satellite imagery.

STUDY AREA

METHODOLOGY

- Two methodological frameworks:
 - Microsoft Planetary Computer (MPC) + Python multiprocessing capabilities to expedite the download and processing task;
 - Google Earth Engine (GEE);
- Similar workflow approach;
- Processed scenes:
 - 149 scenes in MPC;
 - 143 scenes in GEE;
- Derived spectral indices:
 - 5 vegetation indices;
 - 3 water indices;
- Cross-correlation between both approaches;

RESULTS

Vegetation Indices

Cross-correlation MPC - GEE

Water Indices

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

- NDVI shows limited significance and increased uncertainty in our case study area. This situation is also confirmed by other studies, which identified that the NDVI could be significantly affected by the small snow patches when using medium spatial resolution imagery (Koad et al., 2025) – snow along with barren areas can act as sources of bias.
- GNDVI—an adapted version of NDVI—has decreased by 0.15, suggesting a browning trend in the area, possibly due to increasing dryness associated with climate change.
- SAVI and MSAVI exhibit similar trends. Across the entire study area, both indices show only slight increases of 0.04–0.05. As an alternative to NDVI, SAVI is designed to minimize the influence of soil brightness on vegetation signals, making it more appropriate for areas with sparse vegetation (Huete, 1988).
- EVI also increased by 0.02, following a pattern similar to that of SAVI and MSAVI.
- These changes are relatively small over the 40-years period, suggesting a relative stability, but this should not be assimilated as the ecosystem's stability, as large-scale trends do not reflect local changes. Most indices display high regional variability, a conclusion also supported by previous research (Kropp et al., 2025; Frost et al., 2025).
- Therefore, to better capture local vegetation and water dynamics, analyses at local site levels are essential. In some locations, notable increases are observed: SAVI and MSAVI rise by 0.15, EVI by 0.8, and GNDVI by 0.3—indicating enhanced vegetation density and health.
- Conversely, other sites show decreases in vegetation indices, reflecting drying conditions, often described in the literature as "browning."
- Regarding water indices, contrasting patterns are also observed. In some areas, values increase due to the formation of new small lakes or ponds as permafrost thaws. In others, values decline where small lakes and ponds are being colonized by vegetation—a phenomenon also documented by Assman et al. (2025).

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